

DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO THE CONTENT-ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT "IMAGE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS" AND FORMATION THEORIES

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Currently, the problem of forming the image of the head of the organization is relevant for many managers. A positive image allows the manager not only to establish himself in business circles as a professional in his field, but also to influence the formation of the image of the entire organization, which, in turn, has a positive effect on its competitiveness, expansion of opportunities in the implementation of activities, conquest of new market segments, etc. This applies not only to large trading, manufacturing, information and other companies, but also to educational institutions, in particular, preschool educational institutions. Therefore, the formation of a positive image of the head of an educational organization is a very urgent task for modern specialists in this field. Trends in the development of society determine the urgent need to distinguish themselves, their organization among a huge number of competitors, thereby encouraging the heads of educational organizations and preschool educational institutions to consciously and purposefully form their image and the image of the preschool institution, including for a more effective influence on the audience of the implementation of the goals and objectives facing the institution. In recent years, this problem has been the subject of numerous studies from both the psychological and pedagogical science points of view.

The problem of forming a positive image of a leader was studied by N. V. Krotova, E. V. Klepper, A. Erokin, and others.

The development of modern imageology is carried out by such specialists as N. V. Galiullina, N. I. Levshina, A. Yu. Panasyuk, G. G. Pocheptsov, and V. M. Shepel.

The study of the nature, structure and factors of the formation of the image of the leader is carried out by specialists in various fields of science: management and marketing (for example, A. Anderson, P. Drucker, M. Mescon, M. Albert, F. Khedouri, A. A. Altshuller), sociology and political science (A. E. Binetsky, A. D. Karnyshev), psychology (E. B. Perelygina, V. A. Petrovsky), pedagogy (D. A. Belukhin, A. S. Makarenko, V. A. Sukhomlinsky, K. D. Ushinsky, etc.).

Psychological aspects of the formation of the image of a professional leader were covered in their scientific works by E. V. Grishunina, P. S. Gurevich, R. F. Romashkina, V. M. Shepel, etc.

From the above it follows that many scientists are studying the problem of forming a positive image of the head of an educational organization. However, despite this, there are currently no widely used programs for forming a positive image of the head of a preschool educational institution.

Largely due to the specific nature of the activities of educational organizations, a positive image of the head contributes to the formation of a positive image of the entire organization, which, accordingly, opens up additional opportunities for the development of schools.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are set and solved in the article:

1) to analyze the psychological and pedagogical literature on the problem of the formation of the image of the leader and on its basis to derive the essence of the concept of "positive image of the head of the educational institution of preschool educational institution";

2) to carry out diagnostics of the formation of the image of the head of the educational organization in order to find further ways of its formation in modern conditions.

In the context of our study, we will analyze the essence of the concept of "image". The term "image" arose in the West in the 50s of the twentieth century and was initially used in advertising. In Russian practice, the literal translation of the English word "image" - "image, picture" has received widespread use in everyday life, despite the fact that the concepts of "image" and "image" have different historical and cultural meanings. In the framework of the psychoanalytic approach and the theory of psychological motivation, the term "image" is an ideal image that selectively directs the perception of one subject by another, and in turn, is the basis of entire systems, not only in advertising, but also in politics and public life [1]. At this stage of the development of social relations, they began to talk and write about image as a phenomenon of modern reality. Since the middle of the twentieth century, this term has been actively used by entrepreneurs as a designation of an effective means of psychological influence on consumers. Thus, according to N. V. Beketov, "in American and Western culture, the phenomenon of image began to be understood in three aspects:

- 1) image as a phenomenon of economic processes;
- 2) image as a political technology;

3) image as a role model" [2, p. 59].

Due to the versatility of this concept, there are ambiguous interpretations in modern practice. The public consciousness has become entrenched in the idea of image "as a certain value, on the presence and quality of which success in life depends, as does the success of any activity, be it collective or individual activity" [4, p. 12]. Many specialists in the field of management, marketing, advertising, etc. are studying the issues of image formation. A significant contribution to the development of this problem was made by V. M. Shepel, L. A. Lobareva, G. I. Marchenko, I. A. Noskov, R. F. Romashkina, A. P. Pelikh, T. G. Kizilova, A. G. Pronchenko, P. S. Gurevich, L. F. Benediktova, G. G. Pocheptsov, and others.

Summarizing the above definitions of the concept under study, we can say that in modern science (management, marketing, psychology, sociology, etc.) two main approaches to its understanding have developed:

1. The first approach unites authors (G. M. Andreeva, I. D. Ladanov, V. M. Shepel, M. G. Yaroshevsky), who consider the image as formed in the consciousness, emotionally colored and with inherent characteristics of an image of someone or something, close to a stereotype.

2. The second approach is based on the point of view of such authors as O. S. Vikhansky, A. B. Zverintsev, Yu. A. Panasyuk, who define image as a representation or opinion formed by a certain group of people regarding some object.

Thus, image is a multifaceted phenomenon. On the one hand, it can be considered as an emotionally charged image of someone or something, an idea or opinion formed by a certain group of people regarding some object, on the other hand, as a means of development and self-improvement of the individual.

O. V. Bukharkova and E. G. Gorshkova associate the problem of forming the image of the head of an educational organization with the formation of the image in the following areas:

- a conceptual image consisting of a personal mission, professional, aesthetic and ethical values;
- a visual image, including the appearance, style of clothing, design of the head's office;
- a behavioral image consisting of moral values, leadership style and communication style;
- a communicative image associated with such forms of self-presentation and communication as verbal, non-verbal, extralinguistic, proxemic forms, as

well as forms of interaction with the teaching staff and other subjects of professional activity [4].

The formation of the image of the head of an educational organization is directly related to his character traits, the quality of his activities and the peculiarities of interaction with the teaching staff and other subjects of the educational process. Thus, the analysis of psychological and pedagogical research on this problem allowed us to establish that image is a multifaceted concept that includes an emotionally charged image of the head, an idea or opinion that has developed in a certain group of people regarding the head, a means of development and self-improvement of the personality of the head of the educational organization. The criteria for the image of the head of an educational organization are sociability, morality and mental health, acquired life qualities. The formation of a positive image is influenced by objective and subjective factors.

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